

SELF-PACED LEARNING MODE AND TEACHERS' COMPETENCIES FOR AN IMPROVED CSS PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the self-paced learning and teacher's competencies for an improved CSS performance of the Grade 11 Students. This study utilized the descriptive developmental research design that was used to assess the self-paced learning environment of the student respondents at home and how it contributes in enhancing the ICT Skills of the students. The weighted mean and standard deviation used to determine the Self-Paced Learning Environment and to determine ICT skills of the students, the frequency and percentages will be used. The Pearson product moment correlation used to address the relationship between the Self-Paced Learning Variables and CSS Teacher's Competencies to Students Performance. After the analysis, the study found out that the self-paced learning was assessed to be agree in all evaluation areas tested (Self-Study Strategy, Time Management, Goal Orientation, Self-Regulation, Physical and Literacy Environment) to be agree. And also, the study found out that the teacher's competencies were assessed to be agree in all evaluation areas tested (Computer Hardware Assembly, Installer Preparation, Operating System and Peripheral Drivers Installation, Application Software Installation and Testing and Documentation) to be agree. In terms of the perception of the students in self-paced learning and teacher's competencies, it can be inferred that the self-paced learning and teacher's competencies has effectively contributed to the learning process of the students based on the result of level of their cognitive and technical performance. Based on the findings, it was concluded that the self-paced learning and teacher's competency is agree as perceived by the respondents. There is no significant relationship between the self-paced learning and the CSS student performance but in terms of cognitive performance of the students, the self-study strategies and physical and literacy environment is significant. There is no significant relationship between the teachers' competencies and CSS student performance but in terms of cognitive performance of the students, the testing and documentation is significant thus the null hypothesis is accepted.

Keywords: Self-Paced Learning, Teachers' Competencies, CCS Students' Performance